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Camel versus bullock carting and its economics in the hot arid region of the Thar Desert.

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Abstract

A survey was conducted on various aspects of camel and bullock carting systems which involved four different Zones (north, south, east, west) of the Thar Desert. An economic study of both types of carting systems was undertaken making use of the linear programming method. The average working life of a camel was higher compared to bullocks used for carting. The average life of an animal-drawn cart was almost the same for bullock and camel carts. The average daily income from camel carting was higher (about 22%) than that for bullock carting. The total distance covered per day by a camel cart (21.4 ± 6.55 km) was greater than that of a bullock cart (14.9 ± 5.50 km). The camel carting required a higher investment in terms of interest rate, depreciation rate and expenses towards insurance. The overall total fixed cost was higher in camel carting than in bullock carting. In the case of bullocks the total annual expenditure for shoeing came to Rs. 800 / - where as it is not required for camels. The total variable cost was higher in bullock carting than in camel carting. The average yearly maintenance cost of an animal was around Rs15330/- and Rs14965/- for a camel and a bullock, respectively. The total expenditure for both type of carting was almost equal, but total earning and profit from camel carting was higher compared to that in bullock carting. It was evident that due to a shorter pay back period and a higher benefit : cost ratio camel carting was more profitable than bullock carting for small and marginal farmers in the hot arid Thar Desert.

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Introduction

Animal carting provides a gainful source of employment and a regular flow of income to the farmers and other livestock owners in society. The complementary connection between the crop sector and draught animal power adds to the importance of maintaining draught animals. Agriculture and draught animal power go side by side in assisting farming business into a profitable enterprise. Heifer Project International (HPI), a private non-profit making NGO has been assisting tribal minorities who seek gainful employment using camels to transport agricultural and industrial products (Robert *et al.*, 1997). In Rajasthan the main population of draught animals are bullocks followed by camels. The camel, known in many places as the "Ship of the desert", is better adapted than the bullock for survival in the desert. For instance cattle in the central desert of Australia with daily ambient temperatures of 40°C were reported to have died without water in four days while camels survived for more than 15 days in the same environment. Camels can tolerate high temperature, solar radiation and water deprivation and subsist on poor quality thorny vegetation. Since 85% of the gross cultivated area of the Bikaner district is rain-fed, camel carts have potential for making money (Amresh Kumar, 1999). Camel energy may not only be cost effective, but also be profitable and remunerable. The main characteristic features and economics of camel and bullock carting were studied to find out the economic viability of both types of carting systems.

Materials and Methods

Data collection: Using survey techniques, a comparative data were recorded on various aspects of camel and bullock carting systems. Systems using the single camel wooden carts with two wheeled pneumatic tyres (Plate 8) and single bullock wooden carts with two wheeled pneumatic tyres (Plate 9) were studied using a pre-tested questionnaire.

Sampling procedure: The study involved a total of four tehsils within Bikaner district. These comprised four different zones of the Thar desert, viz. Nokha tehsil (south zone) Lunkaransar tehsil (north zone), Kodayat tehsil (west zone) and Bikaner tehsil (east zone). A total of 140 camel cart keepers and 119 single bullock cart keepers were randomly considered for data collection. The selection of respondent was carried out using the multistage stratified random sampling technique.

Economic analysis: The economics of both type of carting system were analysed by using linear programming (Loomba, 1992). To obtain the estimates of maintenance cost of animal (feeding and health cover) and carts, the opportunity cost of owned inputs and actual prices paid by the farmers for purchasing inputs were considered. To work out the total earning and expenditure from different sources of farmers, present day value and market prices were considered.

Results and discussion

The mean values ($\pm$ standard error [s.e.]) of some characteristic features of camel and bullock carting are presented in Table 3. Animal-drawn carting system are common in the hot arid Thar region for all kinds of material transport to and from nearby villages to the cities and within the cities and towns. Both type of animal keepers transport

Plate 8: Single camel cart in Rajasthan, India (A. Pearson).

Plate 9: Single ox cart near Delhi, India (A. Pearson).

bhusa, water, gas cylinders, synthetic yarn and building materials. Saini (1993) reported that the main objective of camel rearing in Rajasthan was to meet the demand for animal power for pulling a cart. The two-wheeled pneumatic tyre wooden cart is made up of sheesham, babool, neem, desi sagwan. The average working life of a camel (14.5 ± 0.50 years) was higher than that of a bullock (10.0 ± 0.66 years) used for carting operations where as the average life-span of the animal-drawn carts were almost identical at about 11 yrs (Table 3). This supports the findings of Jain *et al.* (2000). Most farmers personally involved themselves in carting operations in both cases. But a few also kept some hired labourers to work in carting for them. The average cost of a camel cart was about 17% higher than that of a bullock cart. Most farmers preferred their male camel (96.4%) rather than female (3.6%) for carting operations. This agrees with previous observations (Bhakat and Sahani, 2000). The average working days in a year were very similar in both type of carting system (Table 3). The average working time for male camels was 9.3 ± 2.11 hr/day and for female camels was 8.0 ± 3.00 hr/day. For bullocks it was 8.7 ± 2.50 hr/day. The average weight / load carrying on a bullock cart (8.0 ± 4.11 quintals) was lower than that carried on a camel cart (14.5 ± 4.89 quintals), although a wide range of age of camel and bullock were used. The average ages of camels and bullocks used in carting were 7.5 ± 2.42 years and 5.9 ± 1.74 years.

Table 3: Mean ± S.E of characteristic features of camel and bullock carting systems.

Parameter	Camel Carting (N=140)	Bullock Carting (N=119)
Working life of the animal (yr)	14.5 ± 0.50	10.0 ± 0.66
Life-span of the cart (yr)	10.7 ± 1.75 (9-12)	10.9 ± 1.16 (9-12)
Cost of animal (Rs)	Male 9,500 ± 279 Female 8,860 ± 365	5,672 ± 488 NA
Cost of cart (Rs)	10,500 ± 300 (8,500-12,500)	8,680 ± 450 (6,500-10,700)
Weight carrying by cart (per trip) (Quintal)	14.5 ± 4.89 (10-20)	8.00 ± 4.11 (4-12)
Age of cart animal (yr)	7.5 ± 2.42	5.9 ± 1.74
Working days in a year	240.6 ± 5.86 (235-246)	236.4 ± 8.78 (227-245)
Working time of cart animal (hrs/day)	Male 9.25 ± 2.11 Female 8.00 ± 3.00	8.65 ± 2.50 NA
Total income per day (Rs)	255 ± 3.50	200 ± 3.00
Number of trip/day (km)	3.66 ± 1.25	4.25 ± 1.89
Distance covered/day (km)	21.45 ± 6.55 (15-28)	14.85 ± 5.50 (9-20)
Carrying cost of each grain bag (rs)	3.87 ± 0.50	5.22 ± 0.74
Number of bag carrying / round	18.00 ± 3.50 (15-21)	9.00 ± 2.58 (7-11)

Figures in parenthesis indicate the range value of parameters.

respectively (see Figure 3). The average daily total income from camel carting was estimated to be higher than that for bullock carting. Camel carts covered an average distance (21.5 ± 6.55 km) per day compared with bullock carts (14.9 ± 5.50 km). The average number of grain bags transporting per round were greater in camel carting (18.00 ± 3.50) than in bullock carting (9.00 ± 2.58) operations. Hence the average estimated carrying cost of each grain bag was less on a camel cart than on a bullock cart. Most of the farmers purchased their draught animals as well as their carts on cash payment followed by instalments and loan basis. The analysis of fixed, variable cost and economic estimate are given in Table 4.

The camel cart required higher interest on investment than the bullock cart. The depreciation on a camel cart was also high compared with that on a bullock cart when the scrap value of a wooden cart was considered at 10% of average initial cost. The expenditures for insurance of camels was some what more than that of bullocks, when premium rate was considered at 5% of average initial cost, along with overall service tax at 5%. The insurance charges for carts were estimated to be higher in camel than in bullock carting operations. Here various subcomponents like basic value (Rs 30/-), liabilities (Rs 5/-), 1% of average actual value of cart along with 5% overall service tax were considered. The overall total fixed cost was high in camel carting than bullock carting due to a higher initial investment. The different components of variable cost were considered on a yearly basis. The repairing and maintenance cost of a camel cart was high compared to that of a bullock cart, when repairing of tyre puncture, replacement of tyre and repairing/replacement of different body parts etc. were considered. The expenses towards yearly maintenance (feeding and health cover) of camels and bullocks were almost the same. The bullocks which were used in the city needed to be reshod 1-2 times per month. The total variable cost was observed to be higher in bullock carting than in camel carting mainly because of this shoeing component.

Table 4: Analysis of fixed, variable cost and economic estimates

Expenditure (Rs)	Camel Carting	Bullock Carting
Fixed cost (F.C.)	1,800	1,292
Interest on investment (@ 9%)	885	720
Depreciation of cart	499	298
Insurance on animal (@ 5%)	147	128
Insurance on cart	3,331	2,438
Total F.C.		
Variable Cost (V.C.)	1,550	1,450
Repair and maintenance of cart	19,245	19,714
Wages of operator (@ RS. 80 per day)	15,330	14,965
Maintenance of animal	0	800
Shoeing (@ RS. 50 for 8 iron plates)	36,125	36,929
Total V.C.		
Economic estimate	39,456	39,367
Total expenditure (Rs)	61,345	47,284
Total earning (Rs)	21,889	7,917
Profit (Rs)	0.91	1.81
Pay back period (Year)	1.55	1.20
Benefit:cost ratio		

Figure 3: Various age group of cart animal

Shoeing was not required at all for camels due to the anatomical structure of the foot pad. Camels have soft elastic feet surrounded by thick skin, which is good for travel over sandy terrain. The total expenditure for both type of carting system was almost equal, but total earnings from camel carting were higher than in bullock carting. A similar pattern was found in the case of profit. The pay back period was almost double in bullock carting as compared to camel carting, whereas the Benefit:Cost Ratio was for a third of the time higher in case of camel carting as compared to bullock carting.

Conclusion

The idea of sustainability of agriculture and livestock production revolves around better Use of time, money, resources and family labour of the farmers. The main advantage of this study was to create awareness among the farmers regarding the advantages of camel carting over the bullock carting. To ensure a regular income and sufficient food for farmers and better living standards, it is necessary seek the enterprises which will provide more income and employment to the youth of farmer's family. Such enterprises include camel carting over bullock carting. The camel holds a practical value for cost effectiveness, sustainable, environmentally friendly and socio-culturally acceptable. In fact camels are the life-line of the rural population in many of the remote villages of the Thar desert. The study concluded that due to the relatively shorter pay back period and higher benefit : cost ratio camel carting was more profitable when compared with the bullock carting for the smallholder dry-land farmer in the hot arid Thar desert.

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